

Assessing the role of invasive lantana (*Lantana camara*) in disrupting the native biodiversity of Bangladesh

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Abstract

The overall objective of the study was to assess the impact of invasive lantana on the forest biodiversity, crops and livestock of Bangladesh. Both primary and secondary data were used in this study. It was found that lantana suppressed the natural regeneration of tree species through its competitive superiority over seedlings of native species. As a result, homogeneous and mono-specific invaded understorey in the forests. This invasive species covers created demographic instability among tree species, and reduced tree diversity potentially by changing the structure of the forest. Lantana interferes with agricultural harvesting and reduces the economic viability of certain crops. The soil has a lower capacity to absorb water in dense stands of lantana than in grass cover, increasing run-off and therefore soil erosion. The study recommended an integrated management approach to control biological invasion.

Keywords: Lantana, invasive species, biological invasion, understorey, natural regeneration, demographic instability

Introduction

Lantana is a native evergreen shrub to tropical America. It is now a major weed in many regions of the Pleotropic where it invades natural and agricultural ecosystems. The plants can grow individually in clumps or as dense thickets, crowding out more desirable species. It may grow up to 6 ft high and may spread to 8 ft as a climber with the help of a support. Leaves and stems are rough, and hairy and secrete an unpleasant odour like cat pee when crushed. In the tropics, lantana is a non-stop bloomer. Flower colour ranges from white to yellow, orange to red, and pink to rose in unlimited combinations. In addition, the flower colour usually changes with the change of age. Its prolific all-year flowering allows rapid dispersal, and the seeds are spread fairly long distances by birds. Lantana is a very easy and fast-growing species adapted to most soil types. It is also very drought and salt resistant and seldom bothered by pests or diseases. It needs low water content to grow and can be used in xeriscapes. It is also happy with both humid and hot weather. In temperate regions lantana is used as a hedge plant, which adds vibrant long-lasting colour to the garden. Gardeners in cold climates enjoy this tropical plant as an annual shrub for its fast-growing and quick flowering characteristics. It is invading and disrupting native plant communities in different parts of the world. The study aimed to examine the impact of invasive lantana on forest biodiversity, agricultural diversity and domestic animals.

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. The secondary data were collected from the Madhupur Sal Forests of Bangladesh. Local people were personally interviewed to identify the impact of lantana on the forest flora and crops. Some observational studies were carried out. The content analysis was done to interpret the data.

Invasion of forest biodiversity

Plant diversity and species richness showed a decreasing trend in the Sal forests of Madhupur with the increasing lantana cover. The dense shade of lantana reduced the intensity and duration of light and prevents the establishment of herbs and tree seedlings by creating horizontal stratification. Lantana suppressed the natural regeneration of tree species through its competitive

superiority over seedlings of native species. As a result, homogeneous and mono-specific invaded understorey forming in the forests. This invasive species covers created demographic instability among tree species, and reduced tree diversity potentially by changing the structure of the forest. It became the dominant understorey shrub by suppressing native shrubs in the Sal forests. The dense thickets transformed degraded forests into shrubland. Its allelopathic qualities can affect the growth of nearby plants.

Our natural forests are characterised by intensive land use and high levels of habitat destruction or fragmentation resulting in sharply fragmented habitat mosaics (Rahman *et al.* 2007, 2008, 2009, 2010; Rahman 2021, 2022; Rahman and Vacik 2009, 2010, 2016). Plant communities are more susceptible to invasion by alien lantana. Invasion by lantana changes floristic composition in fragmented forests. Habitat modification and the introduction of invasive lantana cause local decline, and even extinction of native species (Williamson and Fitter 1996). Sporadic tree felling and lopping of trees create localised patches or canopy gaps (Rahman 2020). The microclimatic conditions in fragmented forests are favourable for the establishment of opportunist and exotic lantana. The canopy opening increases resource availability including windows and light regime for this invader. Lantana coverage decreases with the increase of tree canopy closure. Lantana invasion changes community composition, diversity, and ecosystem functioning (D'Antonio & Vitousek 1992).

Invasion of agricultural biodiversity

Some crops become locally extinct with increasing levels of lantana cover. Lantana interferes with agricultural harvesting and reduces the economic viability of certain crops. The soil has a lower capacity to absorb water in dense stands of lantana than in grass cover, increasing run-off and therefore soil erosion. Fodder crops, pulse crops, medicinal crops, cereals and ornamental plants are also highly susceptible to lantana invasion. Lantana leaf extracts cause an inhibitory effect on germination, root and shoot elongation and development of lateral roots of major crops in Bangladesh (Ahmed *et al.* 2007). It affects the economic viability of tea, coconut and cotton (Holm *et al.* 1977). Lantana harbours several serious pests of crops.

Impacts on animals

Pet animals become ill after ingesting lantana. The dense thickets of lantana affect bird breeding by impeding flight. Its leaves and seeds contain triterpenoids, which cause the poisoning of some animals including cattle, buffalo, sheep and goats (Sharma *et al.* 1988). Poisoning mainly occurs in newly introduced young animals without access to other fodder (Sharma 1994). Green fruits are poisonous to humans and can cause death. Malarial mosquitoes shelter in bushes and are the cause of serious health problems.

Management

Cultural

- * Introducing desirable trees to shade out the regeneration of Lantana
- * Gap filling by of rose trees pioneer and early successional species
- * Afforestation and reforestation by native and natural species
- * Facilitating natural regeneration in degraded forests
- * Promoting natural succession in the degraded and denuded forests
- * Stopping further clear felling and illegal logging
- * Protecting natural regenerations (seedling, sapling and juvenile trees) from cutting

Mechanical

- *Digging out Lantana thickets
- * Burning of the thickets

Chemical

* Foliar applications of 2,4-D, MCPA, dicamba, triclopyr, Glyphosate and picloram effective on plants less than 2m tall

* Basal application for larger plants

Biological

* The following insects can be used as bio-control agents: lace bug, lantana leafminer, lantana leaf beetle, lantana seed fly, leaf-chewing moth and lantana defoliator

* The pathogenic fungi *Prosopidium tuberculatum*, *Puccinia lantanae* and *Ceratobasidium lantanae-camarae* can be considered for use as biological control agents

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